

Design of a dedicated ultrasonic vibration cutting system for moulds machining

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Abstract:

With the use of ultrasonic assisted diamond cutting, optical surface finish can be achieved on hardened steel or even brittle materials such as glass and infrared materials. The proposed ultrasonic vibration cutting system contains ultrasonic generator, horn, transducer, cutting tool and the fixture. This study is focused on the design of the ultrasonic vibration cutting system with a high vibration frequency and an optimized amplitude for hard and brittle materials, particularly for mould steel. A two-dimensional vibration design is developed by means of the finite element analysis (FEA) model. A prototype of the system is manufactured for the test bench. An elliptical trajectory is created from this vibration system with amplitudes of micrometers in two directions. The optimization strategy is presented for the application development.

Keywords: Optical moulds, Steel cutting, FEA, Control system,

1. Introduction

Complex surfaces have been widely demanded in various applications including optics, bioengineering, and advanced manufacturing [1]. Ultra-precision diamond cutting is normally used for the fabrication of complex surfaces because it allows a high degree of freedom for the structural design. However, a diamond tool is not applicable for the cutting of ferrous materials, e.g. steel family, due to the graphitization of the tool and massive tool wears in high pressure and temperature. With the use of vibration-assisted machining (VAM), optical surface finish can be achieved on steels, with significant advantages such as smaller cutting forces, longer tool life, and easier chip removal. Reducing tool wear and improving the surface finish have been the key drive of the development of VAM in the past decades. A review on the wear mechanism and existing approaches for the tool wear reduction on diamond-cutting ferrous metals is conducted in [2]. Comprehensive review of VAM of ferrous and brittle materials is also introduced in [3], including one dimensional (1D or linear) and two dimensional (2D or elliptical [4]). Ultrasonic Vibration Cutting (UVC) has been widely adopted for fabricating the optical steel moulds, as experiment reveals the diamond tool wear is effectively restrained [5]. Discontinuous contact takes place in UVC process, so the cutting fluid could lubricate and cool the tool tip, then reduce the cutting temperature.

To increase the system efficiency and reduce the heat generation, a design with a resonant vibration is targeted in this study, which an excitation direction of supporting structure of tool tip that can be arranged as bended or longitudinal depending on the relative movement between tool and workpiece. Bending vibration is referred to as the vibration in up-feed or cross-feed directions while longitudinal vibration is referred to as the vibration in the depth of cut direction. Generally, the transducer has three modes of vibration, i.e., longitudinal vibration, torsional vibration and bended vibration. The integrated vibrational mode, such as the longitudinal-torsional, longitudinal-bended or bended-torsional vibration, will occur when the transducer has a unique structure. If the two directional vibrations have a phase shift of some degrees, the transducer will generate the elliptical vibration [6]. The research on 2D elliptical vibrator development mainly contains two ways of combination: 1. bending and longitudinal modes [7-10]; 2. Two bending modes in different directions [11,12]. The normal frequency of two bending modes vibrator is around 20 kHz [7-10] while longitudinal & bending approach can be employed to achieve about 40 kHz [12]. In these experiments, the amplitudes of the cutting tips are mainly around 2-4 μm in application of hard and brittle materials [8-12], except that of 8-11 μm in [7] for oxygen free copper. Surface roughness of the steel mould is reduced significantly by increasing the frequency from 40 kHz to 80 kHz [13]. A 3 DOF ultrasonic vibration tool for elliptical vibration cutting was developed for steel sculptured surface machining in [14, 15]. The developed tool can be used to generate an arbitrary ultrasonic elliptical vibration in the 3D space so that it is suitable to machine the 3D sculptured surfaces.

Diamond cutting mechanism for the fabrication of optical quality surface on hardened steel and brittle material by applying ultrasonic vibration have been intensively studied by Fang's research group [16-19]. With the advantage of corrosion and wear resistance, high-quality mould steel is primarily used in the molding of precise parts. Fabrication of mould steels with optical quality still requires a polishing step after UVC process. For time being, UVC could be used to obtain surface roughness on mould steels in 4-10 nm in Ra. There is an urgent need to achieve an optical surface on moulds with 1 nm in Ra to remove the subsequent polishing. To meet this industrial challenge, a dedicated UVC system is designed and tested for mould steels cutting applied in the intraocular lenses (IOLs) manufacturing chain [20].

2. UVC system design

The proposed UVC system is demonstrated in Fig. 1, including PC (user-machine interface, programming platform), controller (processing driving signal to oscillator and acquire feedback data), oscillator (providing vibrations frequency ranging from few Hz to thousands Hz), voltage amplifier (magnify to driving voltage came from controller hardware to drive oscillator), transducer and horn assembly (amplifies the ultrasonic motion generated by oscillator). The sinusoidal signal is defined in the PC and software to set a given voltage and frequency, and the PZT exciter generates the vibration when it receives the sinusoidal driving voltage. The vibration from the exciter is transferred by the cantilever-beam horn into vibrations in two directions on the tool tip. This elliptical tool vibration in high frequency is expected to create better surface quality by reducing

the cutting force significantly. The development of the prototype of UVC system is schematically shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the ultrasonic vibration cutting system

Fig. 2. Development scheme of the proposed UVC system

The horn is expected to have vibrations in 2 directions with 1-D actuator at the resonant frequency. The inherent frequency of the horn is designed to ~ 100 kHz. The overall design of the UVC was drawn in Fig. 3. This design includes the horn, the tool, and the exciter with a cooling cover. Numerical analysis was carried out on both the horn and exciter with modal analysis, harmonic response analysis. The modal analysis of the horn aims to find the geometry determining the vibration frequency and amplitude of the tool, while the modal analysis of the exciter assembly aims to find the vibrations modes around 100 kHz. Harmonic response analysis of the horn will predict the tool characteristics during the oscillations.

Fig. 3. Design of the UVC system including a cooling arrangement

In order to make an optical mould with freeform or structured surfaces, a cantilever structure of the horn is proposed, as it could avoid the mechanical collisions. Although some light materials, e.g. titanium alloys or aluminum alloys, have the advantages of high toughness and low temperature rise from the internal loss heating, the rigidity of the cantilever structure of them is low. A die steel with quenching heat treatment was applied to this project. Critical adjustment is the fixation of the exciter part and the horn: making them as a monolithic structure, increasing the coupling surface to cover the full width of the horn.

2.1. Horn design

A FEA study was conducted for the modal analysis. As the material of the horn is steel, the property setting is: Young modulus $E_x = 2.05$ GPa, Density $\rho = 7850$ Kg/m³, and Poisson's ratio $\nu_{PRXY} = 0.27$. The body element is Solid 185 and Meshtool is used to control the size of meshing

(Fig. 4, b). Then the modal analysis is carried out with Subspace as the extraction method, to extract the modes of ten, with the range of 0 to 200KHz. As this horn will transfer the vibration generated from the exciter to the diamond tool tip, the shape of the horn is optimized through a couple of iterations, in order to find a maximum displacement of the diamond tool on this horn. The modal analysis enables the determination of the modes and nodal points on the cantilever beam. The calculated resonant frequencies in the range of desired frequency (100 ± 20 kHz) are fourth mode of longitudinal vibration at 86.968 kHz (Fig.4, a) and sixth mode of bending vibration (Fig. 4, b) at 88.01 kHz. The difference of 1.04 kHz is acceptable for the further test. The fixation position is also confirmed based on the nodal points of the desired modes and marked in Fig. 4 (c); the minimum displacement takes place around this position at a transversal vibration mode of 88 kHz.

Fig. 4. The modal analysis of the horn showing the amplitude in x (a) and z (b) directions and the fixation position on the horn (c).

2.2. Piezoelectric exciter

The transducer of the UVC system contains a piezoelectric exciter and a seismic mass. A longitudinal vibration at desired frequency (around 100 kHz) is generated from the exciter and transferred to the cantilever beam horn aforementioned. A modal analysis of the transducer was conducted to find the vibration modes around the desired frequency ($100 \text{ kHz} \pm 20 \text{ kHz}$), and the frequency of 90 kHz was selected for a better matching with the horn's resonant frequency. The fixation position is also confirmed at the smallest displacement area at this vibration mode. Harmonic analysis of the transducer was carried out subsequently to find out the specific displacement value of the transducer at a given harmonic voltage.

The excitation of the transducer is generated by the piezoelectric actuator through the inverse piezoelectric effect. This PiezoDrive SA stack is a high-performance piezoelectric actuator with a UV cured epoxy coating for improved mechanical and humidity protection. The actuators (SA030305), data shown in Table 1 are matched to the range of PiezoDrive amplifiers and driver modules. To reduce mounting errors, a ceramic or stainless steel ball end can be used to interface the stack actuator to the load. Flexural mechanisms are also applied to reduce bending moments during service.

Table 1 The specification of the piezo stack selected

Range +/-10%	Length	Cross Section	Cap. +/-20%
5.6 [μm]	5 [mm]	3x3 [mm]	140 [nF]
Mass	Blocking Force	Stiffness	Res. Freq.
0.53 [g]	330 [N]	80 [N/um]	300 [kHz]

To meet the frequency and amplitude requirements, a higher resonant frequency of the selected piezo stack is preferred and ideally with a free-load amplitude of 5-6 μm . There are mainly two challenges when using ultrasonic vibrating piezo stacks: quick heat up and high dynamic force. The quick heat up problem can be overcome by using external cooling system as demonstrated in 2.3. Generally, 10% of the blocking force is recommended under static operation, while the maximum recommended preload under dynamic operation is 50% of the blocking force. However, due to a high dynamic vibration as in this project, a higher preloading force may be applied. The dynamic force generated by piezo component can be calculated by

$$F_{dyn} \approx \pm 4\pi^2 m_{eff} (\Delta L / 2) f^2 \quad (1)$$

where, F_{dyn} : Max. dynamic force, N;
 m_{eff} : Effective mass of the piezo stack actuator, kg;
 ΔL : Displacement (peak-to-peak), m;
 f : Resonant frequency.

In this study, the displacement is calculated to be 1.42 μm in cutting direction, the frequency is 100 kHz, so the dynamic force per kilogram is ± 14.2 [kN/kg] as (2).

$$F_{dyn} / m_{eff} \approx \Delta L f^2 = \pm 1.42 \times 10^{-6} \times (100 \times 10^3)^2 \quad (2)$$

The flexure and horn parts are 40 g, so the dynamic force is calculated to be

$$F_{dyn} \approx \pm 14.2 \times 0.04 = 568 \text{ N} \rightarrow 57.9 \text{ tonforce} \quad (3)$$

A preloading force higher than this value is needed to protect piezo stack from tensile force. Due to the limit of the amplifier bandwidth, the

final vibrating amplitude is much smaller than 2 μm . Taking piezo stack SA030305 and amplifier PX200 as an example, the full voltage (150 V) amplitude of piezo stack is 5.6 μm , so the amplitude under 90 kHz (20 V) is 0.7 μm , and the dynamic force is calculated as 22.75 kg force (223 N).

2.3 Cooling system

Piezoelectric actuators dissipate heat when driven at full range with a high frequency. PiezoDrive actuators can be operated continuously at temperatures up to 85 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Continuous operation beyond this temperature may damage the actuator. The flow rate could be calculated from the following equations, and the gas cooling system was shown in the Fig. 3. For a sinewave, the applied electrical power is:

$$P = \pi/4 \cdot f \cdot C \cdot \tan(\delta) \cdot U_{p-p} \quad (4)$$

where, Max. $P = 6.49$ Watt;
 $\tan(\delta)$ = apparent dielectric dissipation factor = 0.15 (0.12 @ 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$);
 C = apparent PZT actuator capacitance [Farad] = 180 nF (+70% @ 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$);
 U_{p-p} = peak-peak drive voltage [V] = 150 V;
 f = operating frequency [Hz] = 100 kHz.

$$\Delta E_{coolant} = C_{pc} V_c \Delta T \quad (5)$$

where, $C_{pc} = 1.003$ kJ / kg \cdot K is the specific heat capacity of air (up to 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$);
 $\Delta T = 130$ K;
 $V_c = 0.18$ kg / h.

2.4. Controlling system

A high-speed amplifier/piezo driver which can process 90kHz driving voltage is needed in the proposed system. Accordingly, the bandwidth is the major parameter when choosing the amplifier. The power bandwidth is defined as the maximum frequency of an amplifier under full output voltage, while the small signal bandwidth (-3dB gain bandwidth) is defined as the maximum frequency of an amplifier with a small signal applied, usually 200 mVp-p. When the amplifier output is open-circuit, the power bandwidth is limited by the slew-rate; however, with a capacitive load, the power bandwidth is influenced by the values of 1). output voltage range, 2). load capacitance, 3). output voltage (peak to peak), and 4). driving frequency. Author did not find any existing commercially available amplifier with a power bandwidth up to 90 kHz. None of the selected amplifiers can process a full voltage with 90kHz, the final output frequency is a compromised result between voltage range, piezo capacitance, and the driving voltage peak.

To meet the high-speed signal updating requirement, a PXI express chassis PXIe-1073 was selected to provide power, cooling, and a communication bus for following modular instruments and I/O modules. Waveform generator and multi-functional A/O were then selected to PXIe-5413 and PXIe-6361 (or PXIe-6363 with more A/O channels). These modules can be controlled by a controller PXIe-8301 that is remotely connected to an external PC.

3. Experimental results and discussion

Experimental rig and control platform were developed to verify the feasibility of the proposed UVC system. The data needed to be acquired is the displacement of the tool tip in horizontal and vertical directions. In this system (shown in Fig. 5.), piezoelectric stacks are employed as core oscillators due to their quick response, high acceleration, high accuracy and high stiffness. The following research aspects have been addressed: piezo-stack dynamic response characterization; system resonant frequency identification; system nodal position determination and verification; and mechanical structure design and optimization. In the system, high resolution displacement sensor is used to monitor tip position and frequency.

In Fig. 5 the devices in this experimental set up includes (1). NI controller for DAQ and signal generation; (2). Oscilloscope monitoring amplified voltage; (3). Piezoelectric voltage amplifier (gain 20); (4). UVC horn fixed on isolation stage; (5). Laser displacement sensor head; (6). Laser sensor controller. (7). PC for signal generation; (8). Monitor for laser signal sampling. The highest sampling frequency (392 kHz) of this sensor was used for the data acquisition with the repeatability of 0.1 μm .

Fig. 5. Experimental set up (left) and the assembled UVC system in the offline test (right)

Due to the limitation of the control board, the voltage cannot be increased over 30 V. The UVC system is modified both from the piezo stack selection and control strategy for a full voltage (150 V) as designed. Different seismic masses were tested as shown in Fig 6 (left), by adding a seismic mass on the top of the PZT stack in the dynamic point of view. Measurements were carried out with a set of masses from 50 g to 100 g (Fig 6, right). The resonate frequency took place at 89 kHz, while the amplitude has significant improvement as the force could be transferred efficiently to the UVC horn. Tremendous data were processed for this experiment with ten groups of seismic mass, and 5 times in each group for

the analysis of repeatability. Table 2 illustrates the amplitude of the tool tip in Z axis (vertical direction) and X axis (longitudinal direction). The amplitude of vibration increases as the mass is added, and then reaches the peak in specific mass value: amplitude in Z axis achieves peak-to-peak 3.0 μm with a 100 g mass, while the amplitude in X axis starts to decrease from 2.0 μm with 50 g mass. The deviations in 4 groups (60, 70, 80, 90 grams) is two times higher than others, because of the combination of two pieces of mass were used in the experiments (see Fig. 6 right). This is attributed to the multiple parts introducing decoupling vibration, although they are fixed tightly with screws. An elliptical trajectory was created by this single PZT driven UVC system with given mass weight (50 -100 g), and the amplitude varies from 2.4 to 3.0 μm in Z direction and 2.0 to 1.6 μm in X direction. This experimental measurement of the tool tips' displacement has a good agreement of the FEA simulation results.

Fig. 6. Experimental set up (left) and the assembled UVC system (right)

Table 2 Amplitude values in ten groups of tests with seismic mass from 50 grams to 100 grams

Weight (g)	50	60	70	80	90	100
Z (μm)	2.4	2.6	2.8	2.9	2.9	3.0
X (μm)	2.0	1.8	1.8	1.7	1.6	1.6

4. Conclusion

A 2D ellipsoidal UVC system is achieved using a single driven vibration actuator. The developed prototype is working under micron amplitudes and ultrasonic frequencies. This novel UVC design is based on a longitudinal transducer and cantilever-beam horn with joint structure, that transfer the vertical vibration to vibrations in two directions. The design aims to reduce the cutting force by creating a high-frequency elliptical vibration on the tool tip with unidirectional PZT exciter. FEA modal analysis and harmonic response analysis are carried out to find the optimal vibration modes, frequencies and displacement at harmonic frequencies. The two resonance modes in longitudinal vibration (X direction) and bending vibration (Z direction) are coupled around 88 kHz. An experimental test of the UVC system with a set of seismic mass is carried out to measure the scale of the elliptical trajectory, and the voltage of a sinusoidal signal at 150 V is provided to the longitudinal PZT exciter. The UVC tool tip vibrates with amplitudes of around 3 μm in Z axis and 2 μm in X axis, when the input frequency reaches 89 kHz. To further increase the frequency, the mechanical structure of the horn and the piezo-stack preload mechanism will be optimized as future work. The numerical calculation of tip displacement is within the range of the experimental tested displacement, hence the FEA model has been proven for horn design and modification in the future.

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